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**EVALUATING DATA REPOSITORIES FOR
LONG-TERM STORAGE OF ACCIBERG
ICEBERG TRACKING DATA**

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<p>SUMMARY: This report presents a brief overview of candidate data repositories for publishing ice drift data to be collected by the Horizon Europe project Arctic Cross-Copernicus forecast products for sea Ice and iceBERGs (ACCIBERG). Repositories considered are: (1) International Arctic Buoy Program (IABP), (2) Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC), (3) European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), and (4) Zenodo. These repositories were chosen from the project's Data Management Plan and dialogue with the project coordinator. The criteria for recommending a data repository include provision of DOI, secured long-term storage and access through standard interfaces, inclusion of a suitable licence and proper acknowledgement to the project, the funding agency and all staff that contributed to the generation and publication of the data set. NMDC and Zenodo provide DOIs as part of their service, IABP and EMODnet rely on external data repositories for DOIs. All repositories have secure funding for long-term storage of data, and offer access through (different) standard interfaces. NMDC and Zenodo recommend CC-BY but allow for other standard licences as well. IABP and EMODnet do not recommend a specific licence, leaving this to the external provider issuing the DOI. NMDC and Zenodo provide acknowledgement and citation statements through their metadata profiles. IABP does not provide information on how to cite data on their website, while the EMODnet portal displays any citation statement from the data set's DOI provider. NMDC is dedicated to marine data, while Zenodo is a general-purpose repository. We recommend using NMDC for long-term storage for ACCIBERG iceberg tracking data to ensure these data are readily available to the Arctic scientific community, public and private sectors. In addition, we recommend using IABP to support real-time access to data for development and validation of iceberg forecast services in the ACCIBERG project.</p>	

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1. Introduction

The ACCIBERG project is funded by the Horizon Europe framework under the call line [HORIZON-CL4-2021-SPACE-01-44 - Copernicus evolution for cross-services thematic domains](#). ACCIBERG “will develop a new iceberg forecast service using remote sensing algorithms, data assimilation and cloud computing, and consistently offer probabilistic sea ice and iceberg forecasts based on Copernicus data” (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081568>).

To support validation of the developed forecasts, the project will collect in situ ice drift data by deploying GPS trackers on icebergs in Greenland waters. GPS data from the trackers will be transmitted in real time to shore. The receiving partner will make data available to other partners and stakeholders.

For service development and validation the ice drift data should be made available in real time. To ensure the collected data sets remain accessible after the project ends, a long-term data repository should be used to publish the data set.

The data repositories considered for providing access to ACCIBERG ice drift data are:

- International Arctic Buoy Program (IABP)
- Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC)
- European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)
- Zenodo

These repositories are described in section 2-5, followed by a short summary and recommendation for which repository to use for ACCIBERG iceberg data. Appendices provide additional information for IABP.

2. International Arctic Buoy Program (IABP)

IABP is an international program where multiple international agencies and research organisations collect oceanographic and sea ice data using buoys deployed through national and international research projects and initiatives.

The IABP web site <https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/index.html> offers open access to the collected data, and provides various data tables and maps for buoy data and positions in the Arctic and Antarctic.

Contributing data to IABP

Rules for participants who contribute data are described in detail in

https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/overview_principles.html.

Some of the major points that must be fulfilled for submitting data to IABP include:

- All buoys should be able to transmit data in realtime to the GTS (Global Telecommunication System) using satellite telemetry.
- Appropriate data and buoy locations must be coded in approved WMO code(s).

- Participants are required to provide appropriate metadata, using a form supplied by JCOMM-OPS (JCOMM in situ Observations Programme Support Centre).

Contacts for IABP:

- Ignatius Rigor (ignatius@apl.washington.edu), Coordinator of the IABP
- Wendy Ermold (wermold@apl.washington.edu), Data Manager of the IABP

Finding and downloading data published in IABP

The IABP website provides access to real-time data from the Arctic: https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/IABP_Table.html. This page provides a list of buoys currently sending their data to IABP (Figure 1) followed by lists of buoys sending data earlier (sorted by year of last reporting). The format of the data files (CSV text files) is described above the table and a download link is provided for each buoy in the rightmost column of the tables. The acronyms used in the tables are listed in <https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/Acronyms.html>.

A Python script for downloading data from this page is shown in Appendix A (“Data extraction script”), and examples of datafiles that can be downloaded are shown in Appendix B (“Example of datafiles downloaded from IABP”).

Arctic Buoys Reporting Over the Last Week												
BuoyID	WMO	Year	Buoy Type	Owner	Logistics	Latest Report	Latitude	Longitude	BP	Ts	Ta	DATA
300234011751690	4701744	2021	iCALIB	ECCC	RCAF	08/27/2023 13:59:57	77.87840	-106.98500	-999	-1.80	-999	
300234060321940	2601516	2022	iceBTC2	AARI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	83.64225	49.68095	1004.70	0.45	-999	
300234060330560	NA	2023	GPS Tracker	AWI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	84.76620	129.85320	993.90	0.30	-0.40	
300234060543140		2019				08/27/2023 13:59:57	82.93480	131.21800	997.60	0.90	-0.60	
300234060726880	NA	2023	GPS Tracker	AWI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	84.76680	129.85120	993.40	0.20	-0.40	
300234060727760	NA	2023	GPS Tracker	AWI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	84.76720	129.84980	993.70	0.40	-0.40	
300234060728940		2019				08/27/2023 13:59:57	89.72720	124.18440	991.60	0.60	0.10	
300234060729780	NA	2023	GPS Tracker	AWI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	84.76720	129.84960	993.60	0.30	-0.30	
300234061162580	2601714	2022	iceSVPB	AARI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	84.05920	53.90980	1001.70	0.38	-999	
300234061164500	2601716	2022	iceSVPB	AARI		08/27/2023 13:59:57	83.62320	45.85780	1003.30	0.39	-999	
300234062735030	4803990	2022	ICEX	USIABP	USIABP	08/27/2023 13:59:57	80.18540	-170.59840	984.30	-999	-1.60	
300234063064350	4802502	2017	AXIB	EC	ICE-PPR(RDAF-USIABP)	08/27/2023 13:00:02	85.63220	-84.59000	1004.30	0.00	41.30	
300234063516460	4701659	2016	iSVP-B	EC	ArcticNet	08/27/2023 13:59:57	71.26640	-104.40780	955.20	1.30	-999	
300234063518460	4701660	2016	iSVP-B	EC	ArcticNet	08/27/2023 13:59:57	70.26020	-101.55460	1008.40	0.65	-999	
300234065495020	4801636	2018	AXIB	USIABP	USIABP	08/27/2023 13:59:57	77.05760	-124.73140	1017.20	-0.40	9.30	

Figure 1. Screenshot of IABP Arctic data table for buoys submitting data (captured 28 August 2023).

Data files provided from this page include surface temperature, atmospheric temperature, and barometric pressure (when available). All buoy files contain at least a date and position.

The data files are ASCII text files, with one line of header followed by the data, one line per observation. Data file Header :

BuoyID, Year, Hour, Min, DOY, POS_DOY, Lat, Lon, (BP), (Ts), (Ta)

Where the columns are

- BuoyID: unique identifier of the buoy
- Year: year of the observation
- Hour,Min: time of day (UTC) of the day of the observation
- DOY: the day of the year to the decimal minute (1.0 to 365.999) of the observation, i.e. Julian day
- POS_DOY: the day of the year to the decimal minute of the reported position
- BP: Barometric Pressure, if available
- Ts: Surface Temperature if available
- Ta: Air Temperature if available

Citation and acknowledgement of data published in IABP

Examples of how scientific papers cite data from IABP

The site has regular (until April 2022) citations of scientific articles that use data from IABP.

<https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/publications.html>

The last 3 citations are (web links are found by google):

1. Brunette, C., Tremblay, L. B., & Newton, R. (2022). A new state-dependent parameterization for the free drift of sea ice. *The Cryosphere*, 16(2), 533-557.
<https://tc.copernicus.org/articles/16/533/2022/>
2. de Aguiar, V., Dagestad, K. F., Hole, L. R., & Barthel, K. (2022). Quantitative assessment of two oil-in-ice surface drift algorithms. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 175, 113393.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025326X22000753>
3. Faybishenko, B., Versteeg, R., Pastorello, G., Dwivedi, D., Varadharajan, C., & Agarwal, D. (2022). Challenging problems of quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of meteorological time series data. *Stochastic environmental research and risk assessment*, 36(4), 1049-1062.
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00477-021-02106-w>

How the cited papers refer back to the IABP site:

1. "International Arctic Buoy Programme: International Arctic Buoy Programme, digital media, available at: <http://iabp.apl.washington.edu/index.html> (last access: January 2020), 2020. a"
The 'a' at the end of the reference is a link back to the citation of IABP in the document : https://tc.copernicus.org/articles/16/533/2022/#xref_paren.40
2. "We would like to express our great appreciation to Dr. Wendy Ermold and Dr. Jennifer Hutchings for their constructive assistance provided during the processing of the IABP data."
3. No formal reference only mentions IABP in the text like this:
"The report D1.41 (2014), entitled "User guide containing quality assessment of Arctic weather station and buoy data" includes a selected compilation of Arctic Meteorological Station data from Canada, Finland, Greenland, Iceland, Norway, Russia, and Sweden, as well as buoy data from the International Arctic Buoy Program (IABP) (<http://iabp.apl.washington.edu/index.html>)."

No statement on how IABP data should be cited was found on the IABP website.

Inquiry about DOI, citation and acknowledgement from IABP

The coordinator of IABP confirmed that the program does not provide digital object identifiers (DOIs) for the uploaded datasets. However, data can be uploaded to the Arctic

Data Center (ADC) as a subset of the IABP data and obtain a DOI from the ADC. He further pointed to some other IABP iceberg datasets

https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/ICE-PPR_DiskoBay_2021.html

https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/Utqiagvik_2021.html

that will probably become part of this subset. (The links above are not findable through the menus of the IABP website.)

The Arctic Data Center will assign a DOI to your dataset when you have provided the required metadata and data (NSF submission standards; <https://arcticdata.io/q-and-a/>). An example of a IABP (full) dataset can be found at <https://doi.org/10.18739/A20V89J8K>. This data set is licensed under <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/> meaning it is in the public domain (free use). The citation statement provided for this data set is:

“Wendy Ermold, & Ignatius Rigor. (2023). In Situ Observations from the International Arctic Buoy Programme (IABP) 2017 - 2022, Level 1. Arctic Data Center. doi:10.18739/A20V89J8K.”

The metadata only provides links to US projects supporting the generation of the data. It is not known if EC projects can be credited.

An alternative will be to get the DOI from another data system, e.g. PANGAEA, NMDC, or a general repository like Zenodo. For example, buoy with id 300234068706290 deployed during the MOSAIC expedition is available from IABP (search for the id on https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/IABP_Table.html) and from PANGAEA with a DOI of <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.940231>. PANGAEA allows for crediting of projects in Europe and internationally. Multiple projects and funding sources can be credited. The citation statement for the dataset above is:

“Lei, Rui; Cheng, Bin; Hoppmann, Mario; Zuo, Guangyu; Lan, Musheng (2022): Temperature and heating induced temperature difference measurements from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoy 2019T62, deployed during MOSAIC 2019/20. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.940231>”

The data set is published under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC-BY-4.0).

Licences and requested/required formats

IABP does not mention anything about licences on their webpage.

The IABP uses text files for data (see App.C IABP Operating Principles (Revised July 2013)). The IABP Operating Principles identifies what IABP considers primary and desirable measurements, see sec 3.2 and sec. 3.3 in App.C, respectively.

Examples of data files that can be downloaded are shown in App.B.

Options for republishing

IAPB does not mention anything about republishing datasets, except that data can be uploaded to the Arctic Data Center (ADC) as a subset of the IABP data and obtain a DOI from the ADC.

3. Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC)

NMDC is a “National infrastructure for marine data that will deliver seamless access to documented marine data sets over important sea areas for Norway to the marine research world” (<https://nmdc.no/>). NMDC was established in 2012 with support from the Research Council of Norway through the INFRASTRUCTURE research program. NMDC is coordinated by the Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and currently has 16 partners (including IMR).

Publishing data in NMDC

NMDC is a distributed data infrastructure where five partners each host a data node, consisting of a metadata catalogue and data server. The data node partners are IMR, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI), Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA), and the Arctic University of Tromsø (UiT). Partners hosting a data node use this to publish their data in NMDC. Partners that don't have a data node publish their data sets through the IMR node or one of the other partners' nodes.

Finding and downloading data published in NMDC

The central NMDC data portal at IMR harvests metadata from the partner data nodes, and provides a common interface to search for data across the NMDC consortium. The NMDC data portal is found at <https://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/>. Data can be searched by scientific keyword, data provider, free text, spatial and temporal coverage.

At the time of writing, more than 3400 data sets from different disciplines can be accessed through the NMDC data portal: <https://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/>.

DOI, citation and acknowledgement

NMDC can provide a DOI through its coordinator (IMR) or some of the partners (e.g. NPI). It is also possible to obtain a DOI from another data repository, and register the metadata in one of the data nodes.

The landing page for each dataset in the central data portal contains a citation statement, e.g. “Angelika Renner (2020) Hydrography in Kaldfjorden, Troms, Norway, Sep 2016 - Sep 2018 <https://doi.org/10.21335/NMDC-1539462099>”. (The DOI links to the landing page for the data set.) The citation statement is generated by the portal based on the metadata provided for the dataset. Data providers can provide acknowledgement statements as part of the metadata.

Licences and requested/required formats

NMDC recommends the use of open data licences, such as CC-BY and NLOD (Norwegian Licence for Open Government Data). Furthermore, NMDC recommends the use of the NetCDF format for data files, but accepts data sets in other standard formats as well. The data provider decides on licence and data format to use for their data sets.

Options for republishing

NMDC coordinator IMR is a member of EMODnet (see next section). IMR can provide for a data set published in NMDC to be available in EMODnet, if requested by the data provider. IMR leads the Copernicus Marine Service Arctic In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre (INSTAC) and can likewise provide for a data set published in NMDC to be made available in the Copernicus Marine Service In-Situ TAC, in agreement with the data provider.

4. European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)

«The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is the European Commission (EC) in situ marine data service of the EC Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EC DG MARE) and funded by the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund. Established in 2009, EMODnet plays a pivotal role as a trusted source of in situ marine environmental and human activities data and data products, serving a diverse user base across various sectors.» (https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/about_emodnet)

Publishing data in EMODnet

Data (and other assets) can be inserted through a public data ingestion service or by one of the members. There are currently more than 120 member organisations and stakeholders. Norwegian members include among others, Institute of Marine Research, Norwegian Petroleum Directorate, GRID Arendal, Norwegian Hydrographic Service, and Geological Survey of Norway. As noted in section 3, IMR can provide for datasets published in NMDC to be further shared in EMODnet.

Finding and downloading data published in EMODnet

The EMODnet Portal (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu>) provides access to a map viewer, data catalogue and an ERDDAP data service where users can search for and download data. EMODnet covers seven disciplines: bathymetry, geology, physics, chemistry, biology, seabed habitats and human activities. Data, metadata and services for all of these disciplines are now available through the EMODnet Portal. The [EMODnet Product Catalogue](#) can be searched by several facets, including keywords, category of data products, time range and formats. At the time of writing, the catalogue contains close to 6200 assets (e.g., data sets, series, services). Data sets can be downloaded through links on the respective landing pages.

DOI, citation and acknowledgement

There is no information in the EMODnet website on EMODnet providing a DOI. When registering data in the product catalogue, metadata giving proper credit to organisation and scientists and other personnel, projects, DOI, ORCID ID, and more can be provided¹.

¹ EMODnet webinar 28-02-2024, https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/sites/emodnet.ec.europa.eu/files/public/EMODnet_Webinar_EMODnet%20for%20Horizon%20Europe%20and%20EU%20Mission%20Restore%20our%20Ocean%20and%20Waters_Slidedeck.pdf

Licences and requested/required formats

EMODnet Physics recommends the use of CC-BY for data products, but it is not known if this is the case for the other EMODnet themes.

The EMODnet data catalogue allows for different data formats. For instance, NetCDF and NETCDF/CF, Shapefile and GeoTIFF, for data files. For services, “formats” like “OGC WMC” and “Web Mapping Service” are used in the catalogue.

Options for republishing

EMODnet assembles data sets from member organisations. Data sets published by member organisations, such as national oceanographic centres, often have a DOI assigned and metadata for citation and acknowledgement. This data is already available through the member’s data system.

5. Zenodo

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is a long-term repository where scientists can store different kinds of digital resources. It is widely used by EU and other research projects to keep an inventory of results from the project as a collection called a community. Zenodo is indexed by OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu>) meaning that metadata for all resources uploaded in Zenodo and linked to an EU project can be read into the EC portal when making formal progress reports. This reduces the time and amount of manual work needed when generating overview of generated results (e.g. datasets, papers, webinars).

Publishing data in Zenodo

To publish a data set (or another digital resource), a user must create an account and link it to a verified email address. Once registered, the user can start registering metadata, reserve a DOI (or enter a DOI obtained elsewhere), funding source (e.g. contract number), upload one or more data files, and (optionally) link the data set to a community. When all metadata and the data are ready, the user can publish the data set. Getting an account and uploading data sets to Zenodo is free. There is (currently) a limit of 100 files and 50 GB per data set, but larger datasets can be accommodated on request.

It is possible to define an embargo period for a data set, if it is not open right away. A dataset can also be published with restricted access.

Finding and downloading data published in Zenodo

Zenodo provides a graphical user interface (GUI) where users can search by free text (e.g. in part of title or abstract), keyword, project, community, and more. Search results are presented in a summary list, and selecting a data set leads to a landing page with download options. Furthermore, Zenodo offers APIs that developers can use to harvest metadata and find links for data download from their own applications.

DOI, citation and acknowledgement

Zenodo provides a DOI free of charge. On the data set's landing page, there is a citation statement, such as

- Edel, L., Xie, J., & Bertino, L. (2024). TOPAZ4-ML Sea Ice Thickness (1992-2022) [Data set]. In The Cryosphere (0.0.1-submitted). Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (Leo Edel). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11191854>

This can be used to cite the data in a paper or in a list of results in an EU progress report.

Licences and requested/required formats

Zenodo enables users to select among predefined licences, e.g. CC BY (Creative Commons) or GNU GPL, or define a new licence (which must be described or defined by linking to an external site). Since Zenodo is a general purpose repository and not only for datasets, it allows resources to be in different formats.

Options for republishing

Metadata for a data set published in Zenodo can be harvested into other data catalogues and portals using one of the offered APIs. This will keep the DOIs provided by Zenodo or provided by other repositories and inserted in the metadata of the Zenodo record.

6. Summary and conclusion

We have evaluated four candidate repositories for securing long-term storage and open access for ACCIBERG iceberg tracking data. The repositories considered are: (1) IABP, (2) NMDC, (3) EMODnet, and (4) Zenodo. The criteria for recommending a data repository include provision of DOI, secured long-term storage and access through standard interfaces, inclusion of a suitable licence and proper acknowledgement to the project, the funding agency and all staff that contributed to the generation and publication of the data set. Our findings are summarised in the table below.

Repository	DOI provision	Secured long-term storage and access	Licence	Acknowledgement
IABP	Not provided for individual datasets. Annual datasets have been published in Arctic Data Center (US) with a DOI	Secure funding from several US agencies	No specific requirements	Owner (organisation) is shown on the data overview page.
NMDC	Provided by NMDC coordinator (IMR) or another node partner (e.g. NPI)	Secured by member organisations through national mandate and/or by projects.	CC-BY or NLOD recommended	In metadata (DIF or ISO). The central NMDC portal gives a citation statement on the landing page.

Repository	DOI provision	Secured long-term storage and access	Licence	Acknowledgement
EMODnet	Not provided. It is possible to register DOIs provided by other parties, such as national data infrastructures.	Secure funding from DG MARE.	No specific requirements	Depend on metadata provided by member organisations, or individual scientists uploading their data
Zenodo	Provided free of charge. Allows data owners to register DOIs provided by others.	Secure funding from EC and CERN	Recommends CC-BY. Offer a list of common licences or define a custom licence. (Includes licences for software)	Data owner specifies authors, licence, funding body, project(s) when uploading. Zenodo provides citation statement on landing page

NMDC and Zenodo both provide DOIs as part of their service. IABP informs that data can get a DOI from the US Arctic Data Center (ADC), while EMODnet relies on DOI provision by external parties. All four repositories have secure funding for long-term (>10 year) storage and access. NMDC and Zenodo recommend data owners to specify a data licence when publishing data. Both recommend the CC-BY licence but provide for other licences too. IABP and EMODnet do not specify requirements for licence. Data published IABP can be ingested into the ADC where a licence will be specified, while EMODnet will display information licence assigned to a dataset from one of the member organisations. NMDC and Zenodo provide acknowledgment and citation statements through their metadata profiles. IABP website provides no statement on how datasets published should be cited, but datasets republished in e.g. ADC or PANGAEA will include metadata for acknowledgment and citation from these data repositories. Likewise, EMODnet will provide for presenting such metadata in their product data catalogue, if provided by the data submitters.

NMDC and Zenodo fulfil the stated criteria for publication of ACCIBERG iceberg tracking data. Both provide a DOI, have secure funding for >10 years operation, and allows for metadata enabling proper acknowledgement and citation. NMDC is a data infrastructure dedicated to marine data, while Zenodo is a general-purpose repository for different types of digital resources (e.g., data, reports, software, webinars). Furthermore, NMDC coordinator IMR is a member of EMODnet and as such can provide for a data set published in NMDC to be made available through EMODnet. Therefore, we *recommend that NMDC is used for long-term storage for ACCIBERG iceberg tracking data to ensure these data are readily available to the Arctic scientific community, public and private sectors.* In addition, we *recommend real-time distribution of the collected data through IABP to support real-time access to data for development and validation of iceberg forecast services in the ACCIBERG project.*

App.A Data extraction script for IABP

There is an example script on the site for downloading the buoy data (Python 2.7):
https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/Download_Tips.html

```
#!/usr/bin/python2.7
import urllib

#—first open and read “ArcticTable_Current.txt” to get the table of updating buoys:
fid=urllib.urlopen('https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/TABLES/ArcticTable_Current.txt')
table=fid.read()
fid.close()
table=table.split('\n')[0:-1] #The "\n" is the "new line" character.
                                #Splitting the table data on it breaks the table into
                                #a list of rows.

#— next cycle through the rows in table and download the associated data:
for row in table:
    buoyID=row.split(';')[0] #The elements of "row" are separated by a ";"
                              #This code splits row on the ";" and grabs the first
                              #resulting element in the created list of row elements

    fid=urllib.urlopen('https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/WebData/'+buoyID+'.dat')
    data=fid.read()
    fid.close()

    writeto=open(your+path+'/'+buoyID+'.dat','w')
    writeto.write(data)
    writeto.close()
```

The steps of the script is described as follows in the “Download Tips” page:

1. Create a file id that points to the file at the url address: `fid=urllib.urlopen(path)`
2. Read the file into a variable: `data=fid.read()`
3. Close the file id: `fid.close()`
4. Do what you will with the data you have downloaded.

A Python 3 version of the script above.

```
#!/usr/bin/python3
from urllib.request import urlopen

def openwebfile(addr):
    fid = urlopen(addr)
```

```

    fid_bytes = fid.read()
    fid.close()
    return fid_bytes.decode('utf-8')

#—first open and read “ArcticTable_Current.txt” to get the table of updating buoys:
url = 'https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/TABLES/ArcticTable_Current.txt'
#url = 'https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/TABLES/ArcticTable_2020.txt'
table = openwebfile(url)

table=table.split('\n')[0:-1]

#— next cycle through the rows in table and download the associated data:
buoyID = [row.split(';')[0] for row in table]

data = [openwebfile('https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/WebData/'+buoy+'.dat') for buoy in buoyID]

# Do something with the data

```

App.B Example of datafiles downloaded from IABP

The following is an extract of (parts of) an active datafile downloaded from IABP

BuoyID	WMO BP	Year Ts	Buoy Type Ta	Owner	Logistics	Latest Report	Latitude	Longitude		
300534060319790	1025.30	4801723 6.42 -999	2020	SVP-B	USIABP-AOML	Svalbard	08/20/2023	13:59:57	76.99800	22.24900

BuoyID	Year	Hour	Min	DOY	POS_DOY	Lat	Lon	BP	Ts
300534060319790	2020	20	48	298.8667	298.8667	81.99700	31.89000	1013.10	-1.66
300534060319790	2020	21	00	298.8750	298.8750	81.99800	31.89200	1013.00	-1.66
300534060319790	2020	22	00	298.9167	298.9167	81.99700	31.90600	1013.20	-1.66
300534060319790	2020	23	00	298.9583	298.9583	81.99600	31.92800	1013.10	-1.67
300534060319790	2020	00	00	299.0000	299.0000	81.99600	31.94700	1013.00	-1.66

The following is an extract from a datafile that is not active anymore (Float your boat).

BuoyID	WMO	Year	Buoy Type	Owner	Logistics	latest Report	Latitude	Longitude	
300234067527430	6301511	2019	Ice Ball	USIABP	CAATEX	02/21/2022	00:00:34	55.59927	-6.35836

BuoyID	Year	Hour	Min	DOY	POS_DOY	Lat	Lon	BP	Ts
300234067527430	2020	10	00	216.4167	216.4167	84.12786	29.12828	1015.20	3.00
300234067527430	2020	11	00	216.4583	216.4583	84.12938	29.14047	1015.20	3.10

300234067527430 2.95	2020	12	00	216.5000	216.5000	84.13054	29.15801	1015.10
300234067527430 2.65	2020	13	00	216.5417	216.5417	84.13104	29.18255	1014.90
300234067527430 2.65	2020	14	00	216.5833	216.5833	84.13077	29.21139	1014.70
300234067527430 2.75	2020	15	00	216.6250	216.6250	84.12981	29.23604	1014.50
300234067527430 2.95	2020	16	00	216.6667	216.6667	84.12848	29.25318	1014.40

App.C IABP Operating Principles (Revised July 2013)

The following text is copied from https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/overview_principles.html:

“1. Objective

The objective of the International Arctic Buoy Programme (IABP) is to establish and maintain a network of data buoys in the entire Arctic Ocean to provide meteorological, sea ice and oceanographic data for real-time operational requirements and research purposes, including support to the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) World Weather Watch (WWW) Programme. The Programme will build upon cooperation among agencies and institutions with arctic interests.

2. Programme Responsibilities

The IABP will:

- 2.1. Maintain an observational network over the Arctic Ocean using data buoys;
- 2.2. Provide meteorological, sea ice and oceanographic data and buoy location from the network for distribution in real time over the Global Telecommunication System (GTS) of the WMO and provide relevant additional real-time data approved for public dissemination;
- 2.3. Ensure data from the network are archived;
- 2.4. Develop and distribute basic analyzed products;
- 2.5. Cooperate with and provide results of the Programme to the WCRP/SCAR International Programme for Antarctic Buoys and other related programmes, such as the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks, International Arctic Science Committee; and
- 2.6. Promote the use of Programme data and products.

3. Observation Programme

3.1. Operational Area

The operational area of the Programme is the Arctic Ocean, including its marginal seas, excepting Exclusive Economic Zones where agreements of the Coastal States have not been obtained.

3.2. The primary IABP measurements include the following variables:

- 3.2.1. Sea level pressure
 - 3.2.2. Surface air temperature
 - 3.2.3. Sea ice motion
 - 3.2.4. Snow depth
 - 3.2.5. Sea ice thickness
 - 3.2.6. Sea ice temperatures
 - 3.2.7. Ocean temperatures and salinities
- 3.3. Additional variables, such as surface winds, atmospheric chemistry, atmospheric optical depth, aerosols, clouds, longwave and shortwave radiation, other sea ice properties such as optics, sea ice and ocean biogeochemistry,

ocean circulation are also desirable and buoy deployment, data collection, analysis and dissemination from these instruments will be facilitated by the Programme.

3.4. Basic Network Density

The Programme will strive to establish and maintain a well-distributed network with observational points no more than 250 kilometers apart. As far as practical, buoys will be deployed to achieve and maintain this density over the operational area.

Participants

Programme Participants can be operational agencies, meteorological and oceanographic institutes, research agencies, data centres, government and non-governmental organizations, and commercial services interested in the Arctic Ocean and contributing actively to the Programme. Participants will indicate their involvement in the Programme by means of a Letter of Intent. On an annual basis, the Participants will review the membership to identify potential new Participants and to re-affirm the intent of existing Participants. Participants who chose not to re-affirm their participation will be deemed to have withdrawn. Participants may withdraw from the Programme with a letter to the Chairman of the IABP. A Participant who is unable to attend may designate a Participant to act as Proxy at an annual meeting by notifying the Chair in advance of the meeting.

4. Data Acquisition and Distribution

4.1. Transmitters

All buoys in the network should be equipped with transmitters to enable transmission of data in real-time using satellite telemetry such as Argos, and Iridium.

4.2. Global Telecommunication System

Participants are responsible to code appropriate data and buoy location in approved WMO code(s) and required to distribute data onto the GTS in real-time (See item 2.2).

4.3. Participants are required to provide appropriate metadata to Joint WMO/ Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology (JCOMM) Observation Program Support (OPS). A metadata template may be obtained from JCOMM-OPS.

Meetings

An annual meeting of the Participants will be held at a location to be determined by the Participants.”